

Software at NASA: Lightning Breakout 2D

ML/AI codes
High performance computing

<https://zenodo.org/records/11088493>

Performance Portability Without Relying on C++

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Unify expression of computation, setup tool and macroprocessor

- Alternative definitions/implementations
- Arbitration on which one to pick

unify computation

- Minimize maintained variants

Macroprocessor

map work to targets

- Figure out the map
- Express the map

CG-Kit

move work and data to targets

- Hiding latency of movement

Milhoja

Mechanism to map work to computational targets

- Figuring out the map
- Expressing the map

Mechanism to move work and data to targets

- Moving between devices
- Hiding latency of movement

National Aeronautics and
Space Administration

Application Performance for NASA Science Lightning Talk

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Workshop

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NASA High-End Computing

- The Application Performance & Productivity (APP) Group provides support for NASA-affiliated scientists to navigate the complex HPC ecosystem
 - Interface between complex high-performance computer hardware and software
 - Complex software stack
 - Complex rules for performance
- Open systems may thrive but there are ecological and Darwinian values at play
 - Inter dependent systems create complexity
 - Complex library dependencies
 - Aspects change and become incompatible, for example
 - Large ecosystems with a plethora of species appear
 - Some software, technology, or theory thrives. Others don't
 - Survival of the fittest
 - Useful systems thrive
 - E.g. Linux, Python, Kokkos ...
 - Systems with abundant feedstock (funding, support) thrive
 - Efficient systems thrive
- **APP is here to help by applying our expertise and observability tools!**

E4S: The Extreme-scale Scientific Software Stack

Sameer Shende
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Presentation at NASA SMD workshop, NASA HQ
May 7, 2024

E4S: Extreme-scale Scientific Software Stack

- E4S is a community effort to provide open-source software packages for developing, deploying and running scientific applications on HPC platforms.
- E4S has built a comprehensive, coherent software stack that enables application developers to productively develop highly parallel applications that effectively target diverse exascale architectures.
- E4S provides a curated, Spack based software distribution of 120+ HPC (OpenFOAM, Gromacs, Nek5000, LAMMPS), EDA (e.g., Xyce), and AI/ML packages (e.g., TensorFlow, PyTorch, TorchBraid, Scikit-Learn, Pandas, JAX, Horovod, and LBANN).
- With E4S Spack binary build caches, E4S supports both bare-metal and containerized deployment for GPU based platforms.
 - X86_64, ppc64le (IBM Power 10), aarch64 (ARM64) with support for GPUs from NVIDIA, AMD, and Intel
 - HPC and AI/ML packages are optimized for GPUs and CPUs.
- Container images on DockerHub and E4S website of pre-built binaries of ECP ST products.
- Base images and full featured containers (with GPU support) and DOE LLVM containers.
- Commercial support for E4S through ParaTools, Inc. for installation, maintaining an issue tracker, and ECP AD engagement.
- E4S for commercial cloud platforms: Adaptive Computing's ODDC with ParaTools Pro for E4S image with support for AWS.
 - <https://adaptivecomputing.com>
- e4s-chain-spack.sh to chain two Spack instances allows us to install new packages in home directory and use other tools.
- e4s-cl container launch tool allows binary distribution of applications by swapping MPI in the containerized app w/ system MPI.
- e4s-alc is an à la carte tool to customize container images by adding system and Spack packages to an existing image.

Exploring Quantum Computing's Impact: Bridging the Gap Between Science and Supercomputing

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KBRwyle

Beyond Classical Computation

Quantum Computing Will Be a Disruptive Technology:

- We are just starting grasping the potential of quantum computing, enabling computations well beyond what classical supercomputers are capable of
- While still a few years from a fault-tolerant quantum computer, it is of utmost importance to start now developing quantum algorithms to be quantum-ready

Multiple Theoretical and Numerical Studies Showing Potential Quantum Advantage:

- Quantum machine learning
- Breaking cryptographic encryptions
- Quantum chemistry / materials

The QuAIL Team is Working on Multiple Topics on Quantum:

- Quantum computing for Earth Science, Aeronautics and Space Exploration
- Co-design optimization of quantum hardware
- Distributed quantum computing for large network problems
- Large-scale HPC simulations of quantum systems
- Error correction protocol
- ... and more!

ML-Based Protocol Anomaly Detection for Securing Space-to-Ground Data Links

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ENGINEERING and **TECHNOLOGY**
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NASA's Goddard Space Flight Center

ConOps and Demonstration Overview

- Typical practice for Protocol Verification and Anomaly Detection focuses on predefined rules for anomaly detection.
- Message Anomaly Detection for Command and Telemetry Systems (MADCAT) is a software product under development at GSFC that leverages Machine Learning (ML) to perform protocol anomaly detection on command and telemetry messages in ground systems.
- MADCAT is a pipeline of signature-based and ML-based algorithms for detecting anomalous messages.
- ML-based algorithms have been trained on valid and nominal CCSDS command and telemetry messages generated by simulations in NOS³.
- Findings to-date indicate that ML-based algorithms can detect anomalous messages generated by simulations in NOS³.

TFIDF – Term Frequency Inverse Document Frequency
OneSVM – One Support Vector Machine
IFOREST – Isolation Forest
HDBSCAN – Hierarchical Density-based Clustering

Developing general purpose segmentation model for NASA data

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Human Oriented Transformer: Free unified segmentation (HOTFUS)

We have achieved using a single transformer-based segmentation model to deal with diverse data sources (ship-tracks, fire, and NO_2 plumes). The next step is to expand capability to different domains with HOTFUS (see illustration) that is built upon foundation models.

More than just a repository: A
thriving community with global
collaborations

WITHDRAWN

National Aeronautics and
Space Administration

Machine Learning for Space Biology

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Biological & Physical Sciences

GAN for Data Amplification

Sample n

Synthetic data Real data

Pending SRS

Federated Learning for *in-situ* Training and Prediction

Pending SRS

Causal Inference for Biological Data

Generalizable to different data types with the ability to learn causal drivers of any feature within a dataset

Automated dimensionality reduction using machine learning selects the most important input variables for causal analysis

An ensemble of causal inference models "votes" on the selection of causal features

<https://github.com/nasa/AI4LS/tree/main/crispv1.1>

Transformers for Biomechanical Analysis

https://registry.opendata.aws/bps_microscopy/

https://huggingface.co/kenobi/NASA_GeneLab_MBT

LLM for Data and Information Collection

- Masking and reconstructing gene values
- Learning the "language" of the genome

300k data points

https://github.com/kevinli5941/RNAL_earner

SMD LLM (IMPACT, IBM)

<https://huggingface.co/nasa-impact/nasa-smd-ibm-v0.1>

<https://github.com/nasa/AI4LS/tree/osdr-chatbot-integration>